

**THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PREPARING LEGAL
DOCUMENTS**

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By far the greatest danger of Artificial Intelligence is that people conclude too early that they understand it.

Eliezer Yudkowsky

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the increasing demand for artificial intelligence (AI) in the era of rapidly developing information technologies and its relevance to the legal field, as well as the various ways it interacts with legal documents. Additionally, the concept of artificial intelligence is elucidated, its emergence factors and development stages are analyzed, and its implications for preparing legal documents are demonstrated.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, intelligence, e-discovery, machine learning, natural language processing, ChatGPT, lawyer, legal document, cognition, narrow AI, general AI, super AI.

In the global context, information technologies are becoming increasingly prominent in almost all areas of social relations. Particularly, the term "Artificial Intelligence" is becoming widely recognized, indicating the growing need for AI technologies. To better understand and analyze the concept of artificial intelligence, it is first necessary to define the terms. The word "intelligence" is considered one of the most fundamental characteristics of human capabilities, manifesting itself in the interaction of various elements within the human body.¹ In the 15th century, the word "intelligence" conveyed meanings such as "the highest level of understanding, wisdom, and acumen." Currently, this word is used in various fields and conveys different meanings. Currently, this term is used in various fields and denotes various meanings. The term "artificial intelligence" refers to computer technology that has the ability to gather information, analyze, summarize, and make decisions based on human intellectual abilities, without human intervention. With the increasing demand for them as a result of current needs, innovations related to them are also

¹ De Spiegeleire, Stephan, Matthijs Maas, and Tim Sweijts. "ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE FUTURE OF DEFENSE: STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS FOR SMALL- AND MEDIUM-SIZED FORCE PROVIDERS." Hague Centre for Strategic Studies, 2017. 25-42 (18 pages) <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep12564>.

emerging. Despite more than 50 years of research on artificial intelligence technologies, the requirement for their practical use has significantly increased in recent years compared to the past. The concept of artificial intelligence was first introduced in 1955 by John McCarthy. Currently, there are various levels of artificial intelligence technologies, including:

- **Narrow AI (or weak AI):** This type of artificial intelligence has the ability to perform specific tasks at a level equivalent to human intelligence. Examples include Google Translate, Watson, Siri, Alexa, and others.²
- **General AI (or strong AI):** This type of artificial intelligence has the ability to perform any task that a human can do. For example, robots are considered general AI because they can mimic human movements, repeat facial expressions, and have learning abilities.
- **Super AI (or super intelligence):** This type of artificial intelligence has the ability to surpass human intelligence in performing any task. It not only possesses human intellect and capabilities but also has capabilities to develop itself and to independently perform complex tasks beyond human capacity.³

With the increasing demand for AI technologies due to growing needs, the requirement for their application has also increased, including in the legal field. That is, the demand for AI in the legal field has increased. Thus, lawyers are performing the role of "virtual assistants." Virtual assistants facilitate legal service provision through the execution of complex and various functional tasks, contributing to the simplification of tasks and the reduction of resources related to time and cost. In particular, in the preparation of legal documents, the utilization of AI has become a necessity, with AI being able to provide solutions to various legal questions in a simple manner and to quickly and easily identify relevant legal statutes and regulations. Specifically, "the use of artificial intelligence in the legal field has been widely recognized and analyzed by the

² Ray, Kurzweil. "Long Live AI." *Forbes.com*, 15 March 2015, http://www.forbes.com/home/free_%20forbes/2005/0815/030.html. Accessed 27 March 2024.

³ Note that even such hypothetical superintelligences might come in different forms, such as 'speed superintelligence' - 'a system that can do all that a human intellect can do, but much faster'; 'collective superintelligence' - 'A system composed of a large number of smaller intellects such that the system's overall performance across many very general domains vastly outstrips that of any current cognitive system'; or 'quality superintelligence' - "A system that is at least as fast as a human mind and vastly qualitatively smarter." Nick Bostrom, *Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies* (OUP Oxford, 2014),. pg. 53, 54, 56.

International and Comparative Law Institute of Britain. They have identified and analyzed precisely which types of AI are used in the legal field, primarily focusing on two directions of AI: machine learning and natural language processing. In legal document preparation, AI serves the following seven main functions:

1. Legal research and e-discovery (as a tool for AI search and discovery)
2. Document automation (as a tool for AI document creation and management)
3. Predictive legal analysis (as a tool for AI predictive analysis)
4. Legal review (as a tool for AI reading and summarizing)
5. Task management (as a tool for AI scheduling and delegation)
6. Automating legal advice and expertise (as a tool for AI customer communication and support)
7. Information and marketing (as a tool for AI learning and marketing).⁴

For example, through *e-discovery* software, a significant amount of data can be collected, analyzed, and verified according to relevant parties, significantly streamlining and systematizing tasks performed by lawyers or legal assistants.⁵ Specifically, discussions among lawyers about ChatGPT, based on natural language processing, have been prominent. According to their emphasis, ChatGPT can provide answers to very simple legal questions and quickly and easily search through and interpret relevant legal documents and related laws. This contributes to the reduction of additional costs and resources associated with legal services.

It is necessary for legal principles and mechanisms related to its use to be developed. If we look at foreign experience, The European Union has its own direction in using AI. In April 2019, the European Union announced its "Ethical Guidelines" for Trustworthy AI with the assistance of high-level experts. This document clearly outlines the "fundamental rights" of Trustworthy AI and reflects the norms that form the basis of the EU.⁶ For example, human rights,

⁴ "Use of Artificial Intelligence in Legal Practice." *British Institute of International and Comparative Law*, https://www.biicl.org/documents/11984_use_of_artificial_intelligence_in_legal_practice_final.pdf. Accessed 28 March 2024.

⁵ Davis, Anthony E. "The Future of Law Firms (and Lawyers) in the Age of Artificial Intelligence." *American Bar Association*, 2 October 2020, https://www.americanbar.org/groups/professional_responsibility/publications/professional_lawyer/27/1/the-future-law-firms-and-lawyers-the-age-artificial-intelligence/. Accessed 28 March 2024.

⁶ Peter, ENGELKE. "AI, Society, and Governance: An Introduction." *Atlantic Council* (2020), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep29327>.

human dignity, democracy, the rule of law, equality, and others. The EU expert group lists 7 fundamental principles of Trustworthy AI:

- establishment and exercise of human oversight;
- technical robustness and safety;
- privacy protection;
- transparency;
- fairness;
- social and environmental responsibility;
- responsibility towards external stakeholders⁷.

These principles not only play a fundamental role in preparing legal documents but also serve as the basis for Trustworthy AI in various other fields.

As "Harvard Law Today" correspondent Jeff Neal interviewed David Wilkins, a professor at Harvard Law School, on "Legal Education in 2024." In this interview, the professor describes his views on legal education and legal service provision as follows: "The accessibility of fundamental legal information to citizens through technology is increasing day by day. The problem is that this accessibility to citizens is a hurdle to the beginning of legal service provision. One of the main problems is that the use of legal tools that could be provided by artificial intelligence is not equally available."⁸ In other words, the professor believes that if the use of AI in obtaining information is the beginning of legal service provision for humans, then there needs to be a well-developed mechanism for using artificial intelligence (specifically general AI, which has the same capabilities as humans and can perform any task) in training legal professionals.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, steps are being taken to incorporate the stages of using AI in legal education and mechanisms are being developed. Currently, we are at the first stage of using AI. That is, we are still in the process of creating the full legal framework for its use and applying it in practice. Therefore, if the legal mechanisms that regulate the use of AI are not created, negative situations may arise as the number of users of AI increases day by day.

⁷ European Commission. "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI." 2019, <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines#Top>.

⁸ Neal, Jeff. "Harvard Law expert explains how AI may transform the legal profession in 2024 - Harvard Law School | Harvard Law School." *Harvard Law School*, 14 February 2024, <https://hls.harvard.edu/today/harvard-law-expert-explains-how-ai-may-transform-the-legal-profession-in-2024/>. Accessed 28 March 2024.

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